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Policy Maker Evidence-based policy

MINIMUM VIABLE SKILLS PROFILE

Policy Maker Evidence-based policy Minimum Viable Skills Profile

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Disclaimer

This booklet is part of the **Skills4EOSC collection of Minimum Viable Skills Profiles (MVS)**, which outline key Open Science competencies for different professional roles. It presents a focused extract from the **Annex to Deliverable D2.6**, designed to support usability and communication. To explore the full list of profiles, visit the Skills4EOSC website (<https://www.skills4eosC.eu/resources/publications/mvs>) or consult the full Annex (<https://zenodo.org/records/15761916>).

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics	MVS	Minimum Viable Skillset
CSCCE	Centre for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement	ORCC	Open Research Competencies Coalition
DMP	Data Management Plan	OS	Open Science
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Social Issues	R&I	Research and Innovation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud	RDA	Research Data Alliance
ETHRD IG	Education and Training on Handling of Research Data Interest Group (RDA)	RDM	Research Data Management
ICT	Information and Communication Technology	RI	Research Infrastructure
IT	Information Technology	RPO	Research Performing Organisation
JRC	Joint Research Centre	RSE	Research Software Engineer
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	T4fs	Terms for FAIR skills

1. Introduction

Open Science mission for this role

The Minimum Viable Skillset (MVS) sets out to describe a shared framework for recognizing the competencies required for policymakers in advancing Open Science. **Policymakers play a key role in creating the strategic conditions that promote Open Science practices and ensure their integration into national and international research frameworks.** They work with stakeholders to establish, implement, and govern policies that support the adoption of Open Science, providing the necessary frameworks, resources, and partnerships that enable the transparent, collaborative, and accessible use of research data.

In the Open Science ecosystem, policymakers serve as both advocates and enablers of Open Science, ensuring that the principles of transparency, accessibility, and collaboration are embedded within research practices and governance structures. **Their role is crucial in fostering the use of Open Science in evidence-based decision-making, aligning policy goals with scientific research outcomes.**

The MVS for policymakers recognises two complementary but distinct roles. The first focuses on developing policies that support Open Science, described as '**Research Policy/Decision Maker Facilitating Open Science**'. The second is focused on using credible research data to inform specific policy decisions and is described as '**Evidence-informed Policy and Decision Maker**'.

POLICY MAKER - EVIDENCE-BASED POLICY

Evidence-informed Policy and Decision Makers gather, assess, and synthesize credible research data to design policies addressing specific societal or scientific issues. They ensure that policy decisions are data-driven and aligned with the principles of Open Science, considering the relevance and quality of evidence to inform their decisions.

ASSOCIATED FUNCTION TITLES:

Policy Designer, Open Science Data Analyst, Policy Advisor.

ESSENTIAL SKILLS FOR THIS ROLE

- Basic understanding of OS/ FAIR principles.
- Knowledge of OS services, resources and research practices that produce evidence relevant to the decision-making context.
- Expertise in applying evidence from OS to the decision-making context, considering the opportunities, limitations, and constraints.
- Knowledge management: synthesising outputs of research and consultation, identifying their relevance to specific issues and stakeholders.
- Basic knowledge of research integrity principles, frameworks and ethical codes.
- Knowledge of the responsible use of data-driven technologies.

SOFT / TRANSVERSAL SKILLS

Considered equally important by Skills4EOSC, these are not specific to the occupation or sector.

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| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negotiating with stakeholders to articulate rights and responsibilities for policy implementation. • Advocating policy measures by addressing the audiences needed to mobilise key enablers and other human resources. • Mobilising and managing financial and material resources, demonstrating trustworthiness. | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complying with regulations and respecting confidentiality obligations. • Using initiative to formulate policy implementation strategies. • Applying systemic thinking to critically evaluate evidence and its sources. |
|---|--|

BACKGROUND ASSUMPTIONS

MAIN ACTIVITIES

- Identifies available OS outcomes relevant to an issue that requires a policy.
- Collaborates with expert communities for elicitation, review and evaluation of data and design of a policy.
- Deploys appropriate policy outcome monitoring and evaluation designs based on OS evidence.
- Ensures inclusiveness in evidence's production and evaluation.
- Promotes and supports OS as a source of evidence.

CONTRIBUTES TO WHICH OPEN SCIENCE OUTCOMES?

- Thorough research is carried out of available open data to identify information that is timely, relevant and credible.
- Citizens and researchers are consulted appropriately considering the specificity of their activity (scientist vs. politician) and role (honest broker vs. issue advocate).
- Gathered information is synthesised to enable design of a policy relevant to the specific issue.

Further information

OPEN SCIENCE SKILLS TERMS

OS skills terms match the essential skills in this MVS to competence definitions from relevant taxonomies. The selected terms offer further information to help identify the learning objectives for skills development. Sources: European Skills, Competences and Occupations ontology ([ESCO](#)), [ResearchComp](#), [terms4FAIRskills](#), [Center Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement](#).

ESCO Research Skills: Increase the impact of science on policy and society; Promote the transfer of knowledge; Apply research ethics and scientific integrity principles in research activities; Synthesise information; Manage intellectual property rights; Demonstrate disciplinary expertise.

ESCO Transversal Skills: Exercise rights and responsibilities; Manage time; Plan; Think critically; Critically evaluate information and its sources; Comply with regulations; Demonstrate trustworthiness; Respect confidentiality obligations.

ResearchComp: Mobilise resources.

Terms4FAIRskills: Knowledge to contextualise FAIR principles to domain; Resource management; Data policy; Data governance; Privacy governance; Data driven decision management.

CSCCE: Operational planning and implementation; Evaluation and assessment; Landscape analysis.

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